

PC1 - A HCI technique for improving requirements elicitation

Per01

PRIMARY PERSONA: TERESA THE TENACIOUS TINKERER

Teresa is eight years old and is a third-grade student at St. Augustine Elementary School, a public school. She lives with her mother and father (Maria and Oscar Dieste) in a dormitory town around Madrid, Spain. Teresa has been using computers at school since kindergarten and has had her own computer at home for a year. She has very occasionally used the Internet at home to search for information related to her school work under her parents' supervision.

Even though Teresa loves to be physically active (she is a keen rhythmic gymnast, dancer and skateboarder), she thinks computers are really, really fun. She uses the Mac mostly to play princess games (dress-up, Dora the explorer, and so), and watch videos on iTunes. Santa Claus brought her a Nintendo DS® console last Christmas. Her current favourite is Cooking Mama 4, although she also likes educational games.

Teresa also loves TV so much so that her parents have decided to get rid of the only television set that they had at home. Instead they have a password-protected Boxee Box where Teresa can sometimes watch TV over IP. Teresa is not very happy about not having TV at home, but she did not like what her parents told about TV "eating your brain" and has stoically accepted. Her 4-year-old sister Alba goes nowhere near a TV since she heard that it could eat things.

Per02

PRIMARY PERSONA: SANDRA THE COMPARER BUYER

Sandra (62) used to work as a secretary at the Universidad Autónoma de Madrid. Pedro, her husband for 30 years, retired from a small family business. They had always wanted to travel after retiring and saved up patiently so that they would be able to do so. The first year after they retired, they went on a tour of the Italian countryside. This left them wanting more. This year they want to return to Italy (but on their own this time). The last trip cost too much, and they want to keep their expenses under check.

Their son has been telling them about the cheap fares they can find over the Internet, if they look hard enough. Irene has spent a lot of time browsing travel sites, looking for tickets to Rome and hotels at which to stay once they get there. They want to visit some vineyards and to spend a day at the Vatican.

Sandra is an amateur painter and is interested in visiting art-related sites. She also loves Italian food, but not all the time. She likes to stay at tourist resorts where she can easily get American food when she wants to.

She is browsing the travel sites in search of cheap fares. She is not fussy about the dates. At the same time as she is looking airline tickets, she is also searching for hotels. To plan her itinerary, she is looking for travel information about several cities that they are intending to visit. She doesn't mind if it takes time to find what she is looking for, but she gets very frustrated when the system does not return all the information she wants. For example, she likes to know exactly how long the flight will take, how much she will have to pay in taxes, and how much she will have to pay to change or cancel a ticket. She does not like having to click on lots of different links to get each piece of information.

PC2 - Adaptive software-based Feedback Acquisition: A Persona-based design

Per03

Linda

Profile: Privacy tolerant and socially ostentatious

Age: 20

Gender: Female

Job: Undergraduate student

Socially affected to give feedback: Yes

Culture Suitability: Middle Eastern-like

Statement: "Giving feedback is a social and community experience and it helps to feel among others".

Goals: Impact the software with her feedback + raising others awareness about the used software + being socially recognised,

Behaviour to feedback:

Linda is an undergraduate university student and spends a great deal of time on her computer studying as well as heavily social networking (i.e. Facebooking).

[Discouragement] In general, she is not a big fan of the idea of dull and typical feedback requests and reminders coming from software applications. **[Motivation]**

However, she gets interested in replying to feedback requests when the feedback requests socially motivate her to do so (i.e. by making her socially recognized for her helpful feedback). This is perhaps due to her likeness of social networking and the time she spends socialising with others/friends on the internet which made her motivated towards socially enriched feedback requests. Generally, Linda is positively affected by one or more of the following social factors to give feedback:

- **Volume of already given feedback:** She gets enthusiastic to give feedback when there is low number of feedbacks already given on a software. She believes it's helpful to increase the number of given feedback which will then result in other users having a better and richer idea about the software.
- **Visibility and similarity of other users' feedback:** Linda also gets more interested to give feedback if she is able to see other users' feedback on the software first and then having the option to accept/reject to give feedback.
- **Social recognition:** Since Linda appreciates social networking and gives it a great deal of her time, she likes to be socially recognized for her given feedback which she believes could help others and make her socially popular.
- **Feedback acquisition as a social activity:** This social factor also makes Linda motivated to give feedback as well as engaging with software. For example, she gets enthusiastic to feedback requests when she is able to visualize how her social friends are rating a certain software and how their feedback influenced the trend in her community.

[Method] In addition, Linda prefers to be approached for feedback by using hints and tips to gather her feedback (e.g. by telling her that she can go to a feedback centre for this purpose and leave her feedback) or by using an online method as a second option (i.e. popups while she is using the software). **[Privacy]** Interestingly, Linda does not mind to be implicitly reached for feedback (e.g. implicitly collecting information about her software usage)

Jack

Profile: Privacy fanatic and generous

Age: 35

Gender: Male

Job: Researcher

Socially affected to give feedback: Yes

Culture Suitability: Middle Eastern-like

Statement: *"I think emails are good if you want someone to actually sit down and write a couple of sentences about how they feel about your service popups and other 'push' mechanisms intrude & interrupt flow."*

Goals: Impact the software with his feedback + raising others awareness about the used software + being socially recognised.

Behaviour to feedback:

Jack as a researcher spends most of his time on the computer working on his research as well as networking with other researchers. **[Motivation]** Jack believes in the power feedback in general and its positive impact. He is a very positive person towards feedback requests and reminders coming from software application.

[Method] However, he prefers to be asked for feedback in an offline way (i.e. through emails or text messages).

[Discouragement] He believes online feedback request (i.e. popups) could somehow be intruding and interrupting especially when he is working on his research and deeply thinking.

[Privacy] In addition, Jack is always concerned about his privacy and therefore he does not accept to implicitly collect feedback from him (i.e. tracking his usage of the software). **[Motivation]** In addition, Jack is a socially motivated feedback provider and his willingness to give feedback is positively influenced by one or more of the following social factors:

- **Social recognition:** He likes to be socially recognized for his valuable and trustworthy feedback which he believes could help others and raise the social awareness about the software in use.
- **Volume of already given feedback:** He gets enthusiastic to give feedback when there is high number of feedbacks already given on a software, This means to jack the software is popular and deserves his feedback.
- **Visibility of other users' feedback:** Jack also gets more interested to give feedback if he is able to see other users' feedback on the software first and then having the option to accept/reject to give feedback.

Fig 4. Jack: Privacy fanatic and generous.

Mark

Profile: Passive and stingy

Age: 50

Gender: Male

Job: Business man

Socially affected to give feedback: No

Culture Suitability: Neutral

Statement: *"I find it problematic, hindering and unprofessional to send me any kind of feedback requests. If I'm not happy with something I will go to their website and complain right to them".*

Goals: Get my voice heard when I need.

Behaviour to feedback:

Mark is a business man and he spends a lot of time on his computer working on his business. He holds a very negative view about feedback request coming from software applications. He does not have the time to be responding to feedback request due to his heavy workload.

[Discouragement] Mark thinks feedback request coming from software applications can waste his time and he doesn't tolerate to be asked for feedback at all (whether it's online or offline feedback request). In fact, he thinks that feedback requests that interrupt him while he is working are an impolite way to get information out of him. Since Mark doesn't tolerate to be asked for feedback at the first place, he is not affected by any social factors to give feedback at all (i.e. social recognition does not make him happy to give feedback).

[Method and Motivation] However, Mark believes that there should be a channel for him to deliver his opinion whenever he likes by making him able to submit his feedback on a voluntarily base and without being proactively asked by the software (i.e. through a contact us form).

Fig.5. Mark: Passive and Stingy.

Richard

Profile: Loyal and passionate

Age: 18

Gender: Male

Job: High school student

Culture Suitability: Neutral

Statement: *"If I'm passionate about something, can't stand negative reviews about it. I would always defend it. As simple as that"*

Goal: To feel better when defending and praising what he is passionate about.

Behaviour to feedback:

Richard is a high school student and he is highly passionate about his new smartphone. His passion makes him blind to any drawbacks of his smartphone. He is not a big fan of the idea of being asked for/reminded to give feedbacks by software applications.

[Method] However, when it comes to something he loves he happily respond with a positive input regardless of the way he is being asked for the feedback (i.e. offline or real-time)

[Motivation] The main motivation that drives Richard willingness to give feedback is his passion and loyalty about certain product/software. **[concerns]** However, the quality of his feedback can be questionable since he tends to exaggerate in praising and defending what he loves.

Fig .6. Richard: Loyal and passionate.

Sara

Profile: Incentive Seeker

Age: 28

Gender: Female

Job: Supermarket cashier

Culture Suitability: Neutral

Statement: *“what’s for me in it?, In fact, I wonder why would people give feedback for free?”*

Goal: To win tangible incentives.

Behaviour to feedback:

Sara is a supermarket cashier and she highly believes in tangibly rewarding customers for their loyalty (i.e. customers win a free product after certain visits to the supermarket). She thinks the same applies to feedback request coming from software applications.

[Motivation] She argues that her the effort and time she spends giving feedback should be tangibly rewarded.

[Method] As long as there is an incentive, she is happy to respond to feedback requests regardless of the way she is being asked for the feedback (i.e. offline or real-time method).

[Concerns] However her response would be mostly positive and not well thought. This is due to her desire to get the incentive no matter how the feedback she gives looks like. This can have a negative effect on overall reputation of the software/product due to the low quality feedback that doesn't objectively represent her experience.

Fig.7. Sara: Incentive Seeker.

Hana

Profile: Perfectionist/complainer

Age: 24

Gender: Female

Job: Hotel receptionist

Culture Suitability: Neutral

Statement: *"I'm perfectionist and I always seek perfection, If I tiny thing is wrong then of course I will speak"*

Goal: To express her disappointment and sometimes ability to criticise+ seeking perfection.

Behaviour to feedback:

Hana is a hotel receptionist and her job requires her to seek perfection due to the size of criticism she receives from the hotel guests.

[Method] She wouldn't mind to be asked for feedback by software applications and she would always reply but mostly with a negative response regardless of the way she is being asked for feedback (i.e. offline or real-time method). She is a very picky person and never get satisfied no matter how good is the provided software/service.

[Motivation] The main motivation that drives Hana willingness to give feedback is her desire to achieve perfection and her ability to criticise any thing.

[Concerns] However, the quality of her feedback can be questionable since she tends to exaggerate in criticism which could eventually result in an exaggerated harm to the software/product.

Fig.8. Hana: Perfectionist/complainer.

Per09

Amy

Profile: Impact seeker

Age: 29

Gender: Female

Job: School teacher

Socially affected to give feedback: No

Culture Suitability: Slightly Western-like

Statement: *"The benefits of my feedback are always not clear to me as a user."*

Goal: To consider her feedback and see the impact of it on the software.

Behaviour to feedback:

Amy is a school teacher and spends a great deal of time on the internet reading and researching educational related topics. She is not a big fan of the idea of being asked for/ reminded to give feedbacks by software applications.

[Discouragement] She does not believe her given feedback is going to be considered or lead to any changes/improvements on the software. She does not even get influenced or motivated by any social factors to give feedback (i.e. visibility of others feedback on the software doesn't really make her want to give feedback).

[Method] However, sometimes she can be tolerant to online feedback request (i.e. showing her a feedback popup dialogue while she is using the software).

[Discouragement] This is due to the fact that she doesn't accept the idea of having her email inbox filled with feedback requests or feedback reminders.

[Motivation] She tolerates the online ones since she has the control to respond or dismiss it at only one click sometimes. In conclusion, Amy can act more positively to feedback request if her feedback is considered and she can see its impact on the software.

Fig.9. Amy: Impact Seeker

PC3 - Persona-and-scenario based requirements engineering for software embedded in digital consumer products

Per10

Persona	
Name: Hiroko Niwa Group: Senior female student in Engineering	
1) Personal Profile <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Come to school 5 days a week, works part time job at restaurants during weekend- Study computer science/engineering, and working for term paper on software engineering- Play tennis once a week- Working with her personal Web page	
2) Pattern of Service Usage <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Daily use of e-mail, browsing the web- use the phone usually without reading manual- Buy new phone at every one year and a half (when boring the capability of current model)- Send/receive some 15 e-mails per day(4lines/e-mail)- Call 3 times per day (less than 10 min. per call)	
3) Specific Interests to the Services <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Easier to write/edit e-mail	

PC4 - Persona-Scenario-Goal Methodology for User-Centered Requirements Engineering
Per11

Persona	
<p>Name: Ayana Ichikawa Group: Junior female student in Faculty of Foreign Studies</p>	
Personal Profile	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Family: Father(Corporate Manager), Mother (Teacher), Sister(High School) 2) Hobby: Movie, Outing for Cafe 3) After-School Job: Bakery Shop 4) Circle: Manager for Football Team (Freshman) 5) Personality: Hard worker, Self-confident 6) Motivation for Job Search: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Professional Work b) Business Category: Trading, International Business c) Participation to Internship: Summer 2006 7) Vision to Future Carrier Development: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Building Carrier for Lifetime b) Build some Carriers in Oversea 8) Licenses: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Driving License
Usage Profile	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Web Access: Access from Home and School 2) Computer Literacy: Basic, Only accessing to Web page and exchanging e-mail, Writing reports with MS Word 3) Motivation of Using Carrier Support System: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Recommended by Staffs of Carrier Support Office b) Access to the Experience Reports of Visiting and Interview 4) Goal by Using the System <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Read through Experience Reports from Home b) Access to Experience Reports and Rich Information to Interesting Companies 5) Daily Access Web Sites: Yahoo Japan, Web Page of School, mixi(SNS), HIS(Travel Agency) 6) Web Sites Easy to Use: Yahoo Japan (Well Organized and Easy to Find Information) 7) Web Sites Not Easy to Use: N/A 8) Operations of Ease: Scroll, Click 9) Operations with Difficulty; Input Characters

PC5 - A persona-based approach for exploring architecturally significant requirements in agile projects

Per12

Persona picture, name tag, and role.

Personalized background details

List of quality concerns extracted from all personas. Each concern is marked to show relevance to this persona.

Persona-related user stories i.e. win scenarios

Persona-related loss-scenarios

Tom:
Age: 59, Professor

- Fast trace retrieval:
- Platform selection:
- Language selection:
- Reliability:
- Extensibility:
- Ease of component upload
- Ease of installation
- Highly intuitive interface
- Extensive document compatibility
- Data confidentiality
- Broad adoption

Tom is a long time traceability researcher. He has published numerous papers that have focused on tracing from source code to design and requirements. He has focused on using LDA, LSI, and various probabilistic approaches. He has also developed algorithms for visualizing the results of his traces.

Tom prefers coding in C++ on Linux. He plans to contribute components to the TRACY project; however he already has an established traceability research environment and therefore may not use all the TRACY features himself.

My user stories:

1. I need to be able to write components in C++ and integrate them easily into TraceLab experiments.
2. Experiments that I run using TraceLab must not take about the same amount of time to run as my existing experiments.
3. I need to be able to run TraceLab on Linux.
4. I need accessibility to benchmarks so I can compare new algorithms and techniques against previous results.
5. I need access to datasets with existing trace matrices.

My anti-stories:

1. I won't use TraceLab if it is buggy and keeps breaking.

Per13

Karly
Age: 26, PhD Student

- Fast trace retrieval:
- Platform selection:
- Language selection:
- Reliability:
- Extensibility:
- Ease of component upload
- Ease of installation
- Highly intuitive interface
- Extensive document compatibility
- Data confidentiality
- Broad adoption

Karly is a new PhD student. She is interested in tracing requirements to software architecture.

She has contacts with a local company who will allow her to access their data for her experiments; however this data is proprietary (i.e. protected by a NDA) and so she cannot share it with anyone else.

She predicts that it will take her about 6 months to set up her traceability environment, but then she discovers TRACY. Karly is quite a good programmer, but is much more interested in the process side of her research.

My user stories:

1. I need to be able to easily combine existing components to create an end-to-end tracing environment. The only programming I want to do is GUI programming in order to create new tracing interfaces.
2. I need to be able to develop my GUIs in C#
3. I need the GUIs to display quickly to the user during the experiment.
4. I need the installation process to be straight forward.

Per14

Jack, 34
Architect

- Fast trace retrieval:
- Platform selection:
- Language selection:
- Reliability:
- Extensibility:
- Ease of component upload
- Ease of installation
- Highly intuitive interface
- Extensive document compatibility
- Data confidentiality
- Broad adoption

Jack is married and has two young children. He has recently been hired by the TRACY project into the role of Software Architect/Developer. He has 6 years of experience as a software developer and 2 years as a lead architect in a successful gaming company. He has taken the job on the TRACY project because he is excited by the challenge of working in a research oriented project.

Jack is very motivated to build a high quality product. Jack has never worked in an academic research setting before. He is very collaborative and is looking forward to working with the other developers, academics, and students on the project.

My user stories:

1. I need to develop the TraceLab framework in a language which supports rapid prototyping.
2. I need the framework language to easily interface with, and call, components written in other languages.
3. I need the platform to provide natural support for the separation of model and view components.
4. I need libraries to be available for supporting GUI development.

PC6 - Integrating Personas and Use Case Models

Per15

Adrian grew up in a small village near Rotown and completed a vocational diploma in crop farming. His parents wanted him to go to university but he decided to work in a local farming company. Although he liked the work as such he soon realized that he really has few development options without further qualification. Now, Adrian is in his third semester. His girlfriend Iris already studied in Rotown and so it was no big decision to study agricultural science there.

For Adrian, much of what they learn is too theoretical. He focuses on what he likes to do such as practical projects and he is happy about his voluntary work in the “Intercultural Garden”. In their last soil measurement project he got a really good grade and could even help other students with the analysis tool. But he let other things slide and he sometimes forgets to go to classes. In one case, he now has to repeat the whole course. He had a fight with Iris about it. She said that he should have a printout of his schedule in their kitchen and that it is easy to create with StudOrg...

<https://www.pexels.com>

Per16

Stephanie had applied to Bellcity University. She knew that they always have many applicants and was not too disappointed about the rejection. So, she started studying communication and media studies in her hometown, but definitely wants to get a Master degree at Bellcity University. Last summer, she used the time between high school and university to go to Bellcity for an internship in a PR agency.

Stephanie manages the Facebook page of her volleyball club. She likes to post pictures from her iPhone, a Christmas present of her grandmother who is Stephanie’s most faithful ‘follower’. They try to meet regularly though they both need their calendars to find a date. Stephanie thought the first semesters would be more difficult but she could manage the workload well. Now she would like to attend additional courses, especially the one on creative writing. She wonders whether she can arrange it with her regular semester schedule...

PC7 - Two-Level Personas for Nested Design Spaces

Per17

Mary¹ has been working for 32 years at John Brinckman elementary school. She especially likes to teach general studies because of the practical exercises she can include in the course. She often thinks she should just take the kids to her garden to show them that there are other things in life than Gameboys™ and smartphones. The eight and nine-year-olds she teaches seem to completely depend on them. She used to complain about this technology fixation to her son Christian

who is also a teacher, but he didn't seem to share her fears. Some weeks ago, he stopped her complaints by switching on his laptop to show her some data his class had collected from a recent biology field trip. On this trip he was fortunate that all students had a mobile phone so that they could use the app he had created to document different plants in the field. Christian said that he would install the design tool he used to create his plant classification app on her laptop so that she could create apps too. He explained it is easy to use and that she will finally have a use for the birthday present he gave her years ago! Mary felt somewhat ashamed after this conversation. Her son was right, the laptop had seldomly been used; although, she did use it to look through the family pictures and she also sometimes played solitaire on it after coming home from school feeling tired...

Mary is 54 years old, she is divorced and has a 29-year-old son named Christian who works as a secondary school teacher in another town. Mary is not a person, she is a per-

Per18

Ben's persona fragment: Ben's parents have a small farm and he takes the bus to school. He likes to be outside and in the workshop of his father, asking him questions about what he is doing. Ben's parents have given him a simple mobile phone to call them if the bus is too late or if he gets sick at school. It doesn't bother Ben too much that he can't really compete with the other boys in his class with their smartphones and games. One of these boys is Paul.

Per19

Paul's persona fragment: Paul's home is not far away from school and his friends often come to his home to play computer games. He has two much older sisters. His father runs his own business and has not much time for him, but at least he buys him everything he wants. Recently, Paul let his smart-phone drop into water, but within three days he had a new one. Paul finds school a bit boring. When his mother asked

him after the last parent-teacher interview why he sometimes forgets to do his homework he complained about it. But today their teacher Mary told them about a two-week experiment on cress cultures they would soon conduct at home. She said that they could use mobile phones to send her their daily observations.

PC8 - Deriving Age Diverse Personas from a Participatory Design Study on Home Electricity Feedback

Per20

Skeleton 1 - MALE RETIREE (age 68)

1. ● Primarily motivated by saving money
2. ● Low computing efficacy
3. Lives alone (per capita usage is high and privacy settings are not needed)
4. Large amount of time at home
5. Possesses potentially outdated appliances
6. ▷ Thinks his household is energy efficient
7. ▷ Little experience with existing energy feedback solutions
8. ▷ Habits are entrenched, needs strong reasons to change

Per21

Skeleton 2 - FEMALE PARENT (age 37)

1. ● Primarily motivated by environmental concerns
2. ● Medium computing efficacy
3. □ Lives with husband, two kids, and a dog
4. □ Works outside of the home
5. □ Home is new construction, with energy efficient appliances
6. □ Wants to shape good habits for her children
7. ▷ Likes to compare energy usage with others
8. ▷ Willing to make behavior changes to cut carbon emissions

One of our personas

Below we will provide the detailed description of the persona we created based on the **FEMALE PARENT** skeleton, *Sophia Harmon*, age *37*, employed as a *Bank Manager* in a medium-sized town

Motivation: Sophia is concerned about her family's power usage because of its environmental impact. Since Sophia makes a good income from her job, she does not worry about her power bill. Sophia wants to be able to monitor her family's energy usage, but is a little concerned that the device will be difficult to understand. *She is not afraid of using technology, but doesn't spend her spare time playing with the latest gadgets.*

Household Demographics: Lives in a *single family home* with her *husband, two children, and a dog*. Sophia's children use computers for their homework, like to play video games, and enjoy watching TV. *Sophia would like to have a centralized view so she can track how much energy is being used in each child's bedroom*. She also wishes to help shape her children with developing good habits in regard to energy usage. Working outside of the home means that Sophia has a limited amount of time to perform household chores, and as such, feels unable to make drastic changes to her energy usage. *Home is new construction, having been designed with energy efficiency in mind. Even though it is equipped with energy efficient heating and cooling, it is a larger home, which increases energy consumption.*

Behavior Change Disposition: It is not always easy to make environmentally friendly choices, but Sophia usually makes an effort to do so. Sophia is willing to make changes in her behavior that lead to less energy usage. However, she feels she needs help identifying the appropriate behavior changes. Does not know enough about electricity to always know what behavior to change. She feels that the

vague suggestions from her power company are not helpful enough to her. Likes to compare energy usage with others who live around her. Her friends and neighbors are also environmentally friendly and she is very sensitive to peer pressure. Is willing to discuss her energy usage habits with others in order to discuss issues related to sustainability.

Per22

Skeleton 3 FEMALE ENGINEERING STUDENT (age 20)

1. ● Primarily motivated by interest in new technologies
2. ● High computing efficacy
3. □ Lives with 4 roommates in a large rental house
4. □ Spends many hours after class working in the lab
5. □ Does not personally own many of the large appliances, but has a great deal of consumer electronics
6. ▷ Is concerned about each roommate paying fair share of bills
7. ▷ Experienced with consumption units
8. ▷ Habits are malleable (if savings are available, she will work toward them)

Skeleton 4 MALE CHILD (age 12)

1. ● Primarily motivated by social norms (pleasing his parents)
2. ● High computing efficacy (enjoys tinkering, but lacks knowledge)
3. ☐ Lives in an apartment with mom and dad
4. ☐ When not at school, is largely at home
5. ☐ Has some electronics
6. ▷ Dependent on parents' intervention
7. ▷ Unconcerned with electricity bill or the environment
8. ▷ Has very few habits, will often forget to turn things off

PC9 - A methodology of persona-centric service design

Per24

Name: Toru Mori	Picture: 	Basic List of Values <input type="checkbox"/> Sense of belonging <input type="checkbox"/> Self-respect <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fun and enjoyment in life <input type="checkbox"/> Excitement <input type="checkbox"/> Security <input type="checkbox"/> Being well respected <input type="checkbox"/> Self-fulfillment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sense of accomplishment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Warm relationships with others
Age: 36		
Gender: male		
Family: wife, daughter		
Daily Life: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • read internet news, newspapers, business magazines • watch TV news programs • study new technologies, and read books actively to meet business opportunities 	Personality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • like to watch human documentary films 	
Career: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BA, Engineering • manufacturing A co. (-2003) • manufacturing B co. (2003-) • Worked in R&D departments in both companies. Transferred to the sales division. 	Memo: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section Manager in 2006 • started to take an MOT (Management of Technologies) course in 2007 • took compulsory in-house e-learning courses 	

PC10 - Cross-Cultural User Experience Design Helping Product Designers to Consider Cultural Differences

Australia

identification and affiliation to social group

"Every Australian I have talked to said the Victoria Bitter is kind of the student beer"

"In Australia if you are a CEO you wear a suit and you have this type of style, not what you want to wear"

"People here talk a lot about food and at which restaurant they went for dinner"

themed, unique features and trendy design

"It is aesthetically appealing if you cover everything up by a fancy facade"

"This was one of the things you expected it to be like that: people have this I would say surfer-style"

"On Melbourne Cup Day they dress as Victorian Royals and wear a hat, it is themed"

Australia is a rather remote area

"The sun is so strong, they even give away free sunscreen in some open-air bars"

"There are a lot of Australian made products, such as Macadamia, Mangos, or also Didgeridoos"

"I experience Australia as a beach-lifestyle country with bad internet providers"

people depend on regulations and simplicity

"Australians really believe in the complete safety of their bicycle helmets"

"Every traffic light has an additional audio signal so pedestrians always know when they can cross"

"Beer bottles are very easy to open, you can just unscrew the crown caps"

people have a laid-back attitude

"I have the feeling that Australians are less emotionally reserved"

"Australians get annoyed when buses break down but they don't stress to fix it immediately"

"I don't think I have experienced such hospitality as I do here in other places"

Icons created by Rémy Médard, Roman J. Sokolov, Luis Prado from the Noun Project

Per25 & Per26

**Ella
Jones**

"I don't like the public transport in Melbourne. Trams often break down and I actually have no clue how the new ticketing system works. But I don't bother anymore."

Ella is a 31 years old researcher at Monash University, Australia. As about 90% of Australians she lives in a city, more precisely in Melbourne, Abbotsford. Abbotsford is a nice neighbourhood only a little away from Melbourne's Central Business District. She would love to live closer to the centre because she likes the trendy designed buildings there but with her current salary and the high living costs she can't afford to live in the centre at the moment.

Ella was born and raised in Melbourne and she never left Australia except for traveling. She studied in Sydney but came back to Melbourne because she appreciates the lesser high-rise architecture. Her parents also retire in Melbourne but she lives alone in a small studio. When she leaves her research department she often goes out to have dinner or drinks with friends in one of the many Asian restaurants close to her department. On the weekends she spends a lot of time in one of Melbourne's parks or at the Beach in St. Kilda.

Ella enjoys living in Melbourne although she is not happy with the public transport system: neither her nor her friends understand the new ticketing system completely. Likewise the Smartphone App, that the 65% smartphone owners in Australia can download for free, is no great support. Consequently she mostly commutes by bike. The fact that she has to wear a helmet by law does not bother her, she feels safer that way and she thinks it relieves her from deciding whether to wear a helmet or not. At work Ella doesn't hesitate to express her emotions. Furthermore she thinks it is important to minimize inequalities among people and that Australian made products should be favoured over imported products.

**Jack
Anderson**

"The more south you go the more busy the people are. But up here everybody is pretty relaxed."

Jack was born as an only child in Cairns, where his parents still live. He is 25 years old and studies Civil Engineering at Queensland University of Technology in Brisbane. With 25 years he is part of Australia's approx. 40% majority of the 25-54 years old age group. He lives in a shared flat with two other Australian students and one exchange student from Germany. Their flat is situated in East Brisbane, a vibrant neighbourhood with a lot of international students and cheap bars.

Jack is responsible for subleasing the forth room regularly to international students as he and his flatmates enjoy meeting new people, although they rarely develop a deep friendship with exchange students. Jack often goes out to have drinks but tries to pay attention not to be in debt. His favourite bar is the Walrus Club. He likes that bar because of the distinctive interior design that gives him a feeling of being in Cuba. On the weekends he joins together with other locals to surf at Pinkenba, close to the centre of Brisbane. During the semester break he likes to travel, in particular to Bali or Fiji, and regularly uses his smartphone to look for travel information. Jack generally likes to use his smartphone to pass time away, as almost 70% of Australian smartphone owners do.

Jack likes to identify himself with the Australian surfer community and usually wears board shorts in his leisure time whereas he disapproves eye-catching status symbols. After his studies he wants to earn a lot of money and would not hesitate to reduce his leisure activities.

PC11 - One size doesn't fit all: diversifying "the user" using personas and emotional scenarios

Per27

“

I have one of those cowbells! I have never used it. I carry it around in my pocket. It doesn't look good, getting in the way of my necklace. I also have to press a button every day to tell someone I am ok...I am ok!

”

Name: Euginia Jones

Gender: Female

Age: 75

Living alone

Associations: Rotary Club

Interests: Fashion, meeting with friends

**Reluctant alarm user
Independent**

GIO'S STORY

Meet Gio. A 58 year old mechanic. Cars are his life. He grew up in a family of Italian migrants. His father was a traditional strict man. As a child Gio had to work with his father after school at the mechanics.

It didn't take long for young Gio to surpass his father as a good mechanic. Gio has now worked as a mechanic for the past 44 years. He has his own shop and is very hard working!

Gio has had only 5 days off. One day for the birth of each of his 4 children and another one to attend the burial of his father. Gio has followed his father's steps; he is a traditional catholic who follows the rules. He does not like doctors much - "they are a waste of time" - but he goes to the GP once a year to get the flu vaccine. Today is one of these days.

PETER'S DIAGNOSIS

LEAVE ME ALONE!

Meet Peter. He was once a top grade student. During year 10, his grades started to drop. Peter became very apathetic and wanted to be alone for the school holidays. His parents thought his behaviour would get better when he went back to school.

One raining morning in April, Peter attempted suicide. His mother found him and managed to take him to the hospital before it was too late. Eventually he recovered from his injuries. Later, Peter told his psychiatrist he had been hearing voices.

YOU ARE A FAILURE PETER

Peter is now 18 years old. His medication manages to silence the voices most of the time, but its side-effects make focusing on studying very hard, so his performance is poor. He meets his mental health worker every week, but the progress is very slow. He has not felt this lonely and isolated in all his life. Now, nobody talks to him unless it is to pick on the "crazy kid". He feels depressed and he thinks that his life is over. Why bother living when it is such a torment?

LOSER!

PC12 - Mobile Technology for Older People : Use of Personas

Per30

Halim (65)

Retiree

He used to perform his work using computer and Internet. After he has retired, he seldom use the computer and Internet any more.

Lives all by himself after his wife passed away a year ago.

He also finds that it takes too much effort to learn about new devices associated to mobile technology such as mobile phone, smart phone and tablet even though he is aware about the benefits of using them.

He claims that he has difficulties in remembering things.

Goal: To use mobile technology with minimal effort and learning stages.

Wan Kamaruddin (65)

Retiree

**Has been using mobile phone for the last 2 years.
Mainly used for voice communication and texting.**

**Lives all by himself after his wife passed away in
Kuala Lumpur.**

He has not used computer much except for email.

**He has difficulties using the mobile phone because
he could not see the numbers clearly on the keypad
and also on the screen.**

Goal: Can be contacted at any time

Per32

Mary (72)

Housewife

Has been using mobile phone for a year.

Mainly used for phone calls.

**Tries to carry her mobile phone all the
time.**

**Only knows how to make and receive
calls.**

Often, she misplaces the phone.

**Goal: Able to be contacted at any time by
her children**

PC14 - Personas for Requirements Engineering

Per33

Commuter Michael Baumann

"The main thing is, that I arrive punctually at the destination!"

PERSONAL INFORMATION

34 years old, single
profession: corporate consultant
hometown: Stuttgart
hobbies: biking, gliding
characteristics: punctual, ecology-minded...

PUBLIC TRANSPORT PROFILE

Commuter
daily use of commuter traffic system
occasional use for business trips
knowledge of a place: good
knowledge of the system: good
ticket: monthly ticket
transport mode: street car, train
alternatives: bike, car
restriction: none
preferences: comfort, quietness, work en route

SUMMARY

Michael Baumann is a 34 year old, single corporate consultant from Stuttgart, who uses and prefers public transport over the car to get to work. He is punctual, endowed with technical affinities and tries to live ecology-minded. Due to his regular travel, Michael knows his daily routine and the public transport system well. His journey is about 35 minutes long and takes him to the center of Stuttgart. During his journey he has to transfer once and therefore he predominantly uses the street car, which gets him to work and back quickly. Michael does not want any unnecessary information during his daily way to work, which already is familiar to him. He only uses passenger information in the event that something would not work out as planned. In that case, Michael expects that he would be informed about disturbances as soon as possible, ideally before setting off on a journey, so that he is able to avoid the disturbance by using an alternative connection.

EXPECTATIONS

- Michael expects...**
- real time information about service disturbances
 - quick alternative connections
 - no unnecessary information

DAILY ROUTINE

Every day Michael takes the street car to his place of work in downtown Stuttgart. He knows his daily travel routine by heart. He must transfer once every 20 minutes. Michael has attempted the same journey by car, but the constant traffic jams and the cumbersome search for a parking space became too stressful in the long run. In addition, he wants to travel ecology-minded and sees his best travel opportunities in public transport, in order to fulfill this desire. Public transport enables Michael a worry free daily routine. His monthly ticket enables him to travel stress free: the journey in general actually affords him relaxation in comparison to travel by car. He has gotten used to short delays and has scheduled 5 minutes of spare time, so as to get to his office at the latest by 8 o'clock. Major delays always get him in trouble with his boss and Michael's day schedule gets completely mixed up. This often continues to aggravate him on his way back home.

PC15 - Crowd Sourcing the Creation of Personae Non Gratae for Requirements-Phase Threat Modeling
Per34

Marvin
 Mechanical Engineer
 Bitter and revengeful

As a Mechanical Engineer, Marvin developed a new design for an implantable cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD) which he planned to patent. However, the MedsRUs company beat him to the punch and filed a patent for a similar design. They are now getting rich and Marvin is left feeling cheated and angry at his lost opportunity.

Recently divorced, and without the funds to support the life style he dreamed of, he has become increasingly bitter about his perceived loss.

Goals:

- To undermine the reputation of MedsRUs by disrupting the ICD behavior of random ICD users on the street.
- To accomplish the attack without detection.
- To cause discomfort to ICD users without killing them.

Skills:

- Strong coding/hacking skills
- Mechanical engineering/device building skills

Marvin’s Misuse Cases which Threaten Correct Operation of the ICD	
1.	Snoop on the data transmitted along the serial cable between the ICDs reprogramming equipment and communication device in order to retrieve the patient’s name, ID, and basic medical history which is all stored in the ICD.
2.	Transmit commands to replace the patient’s personal information in the ICD.
3.	Transmit commands to shut off the device’s ability to respond to cardiac events
4.	Transmit commands to switch to test mode so that a carefully-timed current triggers an arrhythmic test event which could stop the heart entirely.

Angela is a medical researcher who believes that current practices in heart monitoring and defibrillation are not as effective as they might be. She has run some experiments on lab rats but wishes to experiment with human subjects. She knows that she needs to first go through the process of human-subject research approval, but before doing so, she has decided to try some informal experiments on her own group of patients. This way, she can short-circuit the otherwise laborious task of getting her study approved. She needs a break-through discovery to boost her career, which has currently stagnated.

Angela
 Medical Doctor
 Ambitious researcher

- Skills:**
- Medical training to plan new therapy patterns.
 - Lacks technical skills to tamper with the ICD command log in order to hide the unorthodox commands she sends to the device. However, she has persuaded her boyfriend, who is a skilled hacker, to write a program to purge entries from the log.

- Goals:**
- To perform a non-approved study on her patients by testing a variety of non-approved pulsing therapies.
 - To cover her tracks by purging her illegal commands from the ICD logs.

Angela's Misuse Cases which Threaten Correct Operation of the ICD	
1.	Set heart rate cut-off rate and therapy initiation delays to experimental levels outside normal bounds.
2.	The ICD stores a record of any changes in setting, therefore Angela will tamper with the ICD command audit log on both the ICD and the external history database to remove all record of the current change in settings.
3.	During normal operation, the ICD stores a short-term log of ICD events. This log includes events such as ICD pulsing/therapy events, and sensor readings. Angela's boyfriend has written code to remove evidence of the illegal study by purging the historical log.

PC16 - Creating Rich and Representative Personas by Discovering Affordances Per36 (PC1), Per37 (PC2), Per38 (PC3)

1. PC1, characterized as "Quizzer", heavily uses quiz-related features by starting, doing and submitting quizzes, reviewing quiz responses, and checking the summary of their quiz attempts.
2. PC2, characterized as "Time Manager", uses calendar and scheduler features by creating and updating

calendar events, and adding, checking, or removing booking schedules. They use the Moodle calendar to remind themselves of specific deadlines and events. Also, they use the scheduler to make appointments with the instructor or TA for meetings.

3. PC3, characterized as "Forumer", frequently checks the main pages of forums and the discussion pages for various forums. They also tend to check the list of users and their profile pages. Moreover, they tend to check their grades.

PC17- Revisiting personas: the making-of for special user groups Per39 (Albert), Per40 (Anna)

<p>Name: Anna Age: 72 Location: Sweden Occupation: Retired</p> <p>Social contacts: Until a few months ago, Anna was in regular contact with her 3 best friends Susan, Anika and Leonie, who she has known for a couple of years from the cycling club. They often met each other, if only just to go for a walk. But due to her restrictions in mobility, she doesn't see them as often as she would like to. Until recently, Anna regularly took care of her two grandchildren Simon and Mark (aged 3 and 5 years), as their mother had just started a new job. Anna likes to take care of the two boys, because she enjoys the feeling of being useful. Since her rheumatism has gotten worse, she only takes care of them occasionally, because she quickly feels overstrained. She regularly meets her son and daughter-in-law who support her in terms of daily activities. Her son is especially concerned about her physical condition and would wish to have more time to take care of his mother.</p> <p>Interest and experience in new communication technologies: Anna is interested in new communication technologies and is familiar with her mobile phone, e.g. she knows how to write a text message. Furthermore, she sometimes uses Facebook to stay in contact with her friends. Although her available budget per month is more than 1000 Euros, she is not willing to spend money on new communication technologies.</p> <p>Requirements: 1) include formats that support her staying as physically fit as possible, 2) provide possibilities to encourage the social contact with her family/friends, 3) provide a possibility that enables Anna to contact her caregiver/family, to ensure constant care conditions, 4) provide a possibility to involve Anna's family, in terms of care and 5) support Anna regarding her chronic disease and other issues regarding her daily activities</p>	
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Per41 (Sarah), Per42 (Tobias)

Name: Sarah
Age: 8
Location: Australia
Occupation: Third grade student in elementary school

Computer Experience: Sarah has initially learned how to handle computers through a computer for kids. Additionally, she uses the computer at school for didactic games and information seeking. She likes downloading music, which she learned from her older brother. She does not have her own Facebook account, but her mother does and sometimes they are on Facebook together. She would like to have her own account, but her mother does not want her to as she thinks Sarah is too young. Sarah has an email account for exchanging photos, but she does not use it to write or read text.

Goals: Love, security and independence. Therefore, Sarah needs to cope with leaving the security and safety of home and parents to enter the riskier but more exciting world of peers. To develop successfully, she must have the opportunity to safely explore beyond the world of her family, be exposed to a range of new experiences and be welcomed back when ready to return [1]. For Sarah, even her grandparents expand her world as they do not have a close relationship right now.

Frustrations and pain points: Needing frequent or a lot of help when using the system

Primary usage reasons: 1) establishing a steady relationship with her grandparents, getting to know them better and 2) communication supported by video (to see her grandparents, which is not possible on the phone)

Name: Tobias
Age: 12
Location: Austria
Occupation: Second grade student in secondary school

Games: Tobias prefers playing games of skill or action on the computer or on the console. However, he dislikes games, which primarily aim at killing and violence. On the computer, he also likes role plays, like Sims or "Die Stämme", as long as the fellow players do not cheat or think that they are better than him. In his spare time, he is also fond of tile-based games, e.g., doing jigsaws with his parents or playing card games with his friends.

Playing Venues: In school, Tobias prefers playing ball games in the gym or on the sports ground, as well as playing tag in the schoolyard. He perceives the entrance area and the corridor as being too loud, thus he rather plays in the classroom if the teacher allows to. In breaks, Tobias rarely plays, as he is too distracted.

Game Features: Tobias thinks that games need to be fun and exciting. Furthermore, he wishes for good and realistic graphics. Players should not only be able to choose their tokens, but also configure them by themselves. Tobias prefers games, in which it is possible to collect as many points as possible or in which the winner is the one, who reaches the goal first and the last loses. As soon as a game is too difficult and he cannot go further or if the end cannot be foreseen, Tobias quickly loses interest in the game. In order to avoid this, he requests game instructions not to be too long and complex, but short and appropriate for children by using understandable pictures. He also prefers having the rules of the game explained within a trial. Preferably, Tobias controls computer games with mouse and keyboard, as long as the configuration of the buttons is described accurately at the beginning of the game.

PC18 - Using probes to create child personas for games
Per43

	<p>Name: Tobias</p> <p>Age: 12 years</p> <p>Place of Residence: Graz, Austria</p> <p>School: Grammar School Graz West</p>
<p>Games: Tobias prefers playing games of skill or action on the computer or on the console. However, he dislikes games, which primarily aim at killing and violence. On the computer he also likes role plays, like Sims or "Die Stämme" as long as the fellow players do not cheat or think that they are better than him. In his spare time he is also fond of tile-based games, e.g., doing jigsaws with his parents or playing card games with his friends.</p>	
<p>Playing Venues: In school, Tobias prefers playing ball games in the gym or on the sports ground as well as playing tag in the schoolyard. He perceives the entrance area and the corridor as being too loud, thus he rather plays in the classroom if the teacher allows to. In breaks Tobias does rarely play, as he is too distracted. When Tobias is at home, he likes playing in the child's room a few times per week due to its coziness and quietness, so he does not get distracted while playing there. Since Tobias' game console is placed in the living room, he also likes playing there. Furthermore, when his friends are visiting him, they play in the living room games of dice or cards, e.g., ludo. If the weather is fine, he also plays in the garden with his friends, mainly tag and soccer, or card games (e.g., UNO) on the terrace. He does not like playing on the street, as it is too dangerous there. Additionally, he avoids playing in the kitchen as it is often very loud there.</p>	
<p>Playtimes: In school Tobias plays rather infrequently, except for the gym class. But in his spare time, on weekends or holidays he plays up to two hours per day as long as there is nothing else to do. Tobias' parents do not allow him to play in case he needs to learn, has an exam on the next day or a test in school. Furthermore, he is not allowed to play when he is expected to help his parents or tidy up his room. He is also banned from playing e.g., as soon as he does not adhere to rules or is cheeky.</p>	
<p>Game Features: Tobias thinks that games need to be fun and exciting. Furthermore, he wishes for good and realistic graphics. Players should not only be able to choose their token, but also configure them by themselves. The plot of the game should not be repeated frequently and the levels should not be too difficult. Tobias prefers games, in which it is possible to collect as many points as possible or in which the one wins, who reaches the goal first and the one loses, who is there last. As soon as a game is too difficult and he cannot get further, or if the end cannot be foreseen, Tobias loses interest in the game quickly. In order to avoid this, he requests game instructions to be not too long and complex, but short and appropriate for children by using understandable pictures. He also prefers having the rules of the game explained within a trial. Preferably Tobias controls computer games with mouse and keyboard, as long as the configuration of the buttons is described accurately at the beginning of the game. Several times a week he also likes playing games with a controller, e.g., the move controller on the console.</p>	

Table 2: Persona for Cluster 1 (translated from German)

PC19 - Human-computer interaction and the older adult: an example using user research and personas

Per44

John

[33]

Background

John is a 70-year-old man that suffers from a dangerous type of diabetes. He is a very social person and a good fork. John does not understand his disease and has problems handling it.

John also has problems remembering his medication and his medical appointments.

Goals and Motivation

John wants to be better informed so that he can act effectively and avoid staying at the hospital.

John wants to have a system that remembers him to take his medication and of his medical appointments.

PC20 - A persona-based modelling for contextual requirements Per45

Mary Collins (Persona 1)

Age: 70 years
Profession: Retired

Attributes

- Live alone in a small house;
- Does not have a housekeeper, only diarist every 15 days;
- Does other household chores;
- Fell at home once, but did not fracture any bone;
- Has osteoporosis type 2 at an early stage;
- Has diabetes, high blood pressure and heart problems;
- She is diurnal but wakes up twice at night to go to the bathroom;
- Has 2 children who lives in their homes;
- Don't have Wi-Fi at home.

Goals

- To avoid frustrating experiences with technologies;
- To not to worry with her children;
- To feel safe by not falling down at home;
- To have quality of life.

PC21 - Capturing multi-stakeholder needs in customer-centric cloud service design
Per46

Liz –
Retention
Manager

- **Persona type:** Retentions manager
- **Name:** Liz
- **Age:** 30-45 years old
- **Location:** Southwark
- **Technical comfort:** Medium

- **Backstory**
 - Bachelors degree in business management
 - 5-10 years experience leading teams in publishing sector
 - Strategic thinker
- **Motivations**
 - Maximise customer retention
 - Identify key drivers of customer churn
 - Implement a programme of proactive & reactive measure to reduce observed churn trends
 - Develop targeted marketing campaigns for specific publications/market segments

- **Frustrations**
 - Over-reliance on Excel and Access
 - Latency period for generating requested analysis reports
 - Chinese walls between departments sometimes more of obstacle than benefit
- **Their ideal experience**
 - Greater flexibility of data polling, analysis and reporting
 - Regular updates of both quantitative & qualitative performance metrics
 - Data aggregation and dissection capabilities
 - Increased cooperation and integration of activities across departments
 - Executive overview across departments with consistent integration of latest information

- **The Ideal experience**
 - What features and content will help them have a great experience?

PC22 - Building a National E-Service using Sentire experience report on the use of Sentire: A volere-based requirements framework driven by calibrated personas and simulated user feedback
Per47 (Doris Piscopo) & Per48 (Mary Piscopo)

MCCAA CAP - PERSONA PROFILE	MCCAA CAP - PERSONA PROFILE
<p>Doris Piscopo (Housewife)</p>	<p>Mary Piscopo (Retired teacher)</p>
<p>Mary is a complete tech-newbie. She took an introductory course on basic browsing offered by her local council. She's weary of online banking and shopping, but she's willing to try as she heard that it's safe and convenient. Sometimes her children assist her in her online ventures. However she often ends up having to call someone to help her out of a situation or to get re-assurance. Sometimes Mary can be gullible and falls for scams.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Computer skills: Elementary• Education: Up to primary school• Attitudes: Her lack of self-confidence on the use of computers keeps her from using e-services. She's afraid of breaking things	<p>Mary is a beginner on the use of computers and the internet however she has some experience due to work related matters. She's weary of online banking and shopping, but she's willing to try as she heard that it's safe and convenient. Sometimes her children assist her in her online ventures.</p> <p>Mary's also very careful with her online activities but she tries to keep up with technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Computer skills: Basic• Education: Up to secondary school• Attitudes: She's not afraid to try new things and make mistakes, and she's willing to seek help to get things done

PC23 - SmartWalk: personas and scenarios definition and functional requirements

Per49

1) *Persona 1 – active old person*

Name: António Silva [Personal factor].

Age: 72 years old [Personal factor].

António lives in Águeda. He is widowed. He is a retired football coach [Personal factor].

António has a good level of technological literacy and knows very well how to work with electronic devices [Personal factor], specially his smartphone that he uses to read digital newspapers and be informed about football league [Daily routine].

He has heart problems and his health condition requires regular monitoring and daily medication [Health condition], which António controls himself with a smartwatch that his daughter gave him on his last birthday [Daily routine].

Due to his health condition, António has a habit to do long walks every morning. Sometimes, he challenges his friend and neighbour to walk with him [Daily routine].

Per50

2) *Persona 2 – sedentary old person*

Name: Isabel Rocha [Personal factor].

Age: 70 years old [Personal factor].

Isabel lives in Águeda with her husband José. She is a housewife [Personal factor].

Isabel has three grandsons. They have a good relationship, but nowadays they visit her less due to their jobs. They have been trying to persuade Isabel to use Facebook, but she does not know how that works [Personal factor]. She only uses the

mobile phone to make calls to her family and friends [Daily routine].

Isabel has a garden that she takes care every day [Activity type].

In the last week, she went to her family doctor that told her that she was overweight and that she has to exercise more and he recommended daily walks [Health condition].

Isabel does not like to walk alone (her husband cannot go with her due to health problems) and she thinks that it is silly to walk without nothing interesting to see. She would prefer that she could combine walking with discovering interesting places and cultural events in the town [Personal factor].

Per51

3) *Persona 3 – Health professional*

Name: Sara Tavares [Personal factor].

Age: 27 years old [Personal factor].

Sara works in the Primary Healthcare Centre of Águeda [Personal factor]. In her job, she must consult all the medical records to define the intervention to each of her patients. She would like this process to be easier and faster [Participation type]. She is not so good in what concerns to technological solutions, but she is willing to learn, because she thinks that electronic records and digital applications can improve efficiency [Personal factor].

Sara knows applications in other health area, like nursing, and she thinks that they are very difficult to use. When an application exists to physiotherapy she hopes that it will be more intuitive and user friendly [Personal factors].

PC24 - Personas in the middle: automated support for creating personas as focal points in feature gathering forums

Per52

Joe
Insurance Seeker

- Fast and responsive
- Scales to support 10,000 simultaneous visitors
- Graceful degradation under excessive loads
- Interfaces with heterogeneous systems
- User-centric Design
- Privacy of healthcare data
- Privacy of financial data
- Accurate information

Joe is married and has two children. He was previously employed as a construction worker, but after a biking accident he has been unable to work full-time. He spends much of his time watching television. He has had no health-care insurance since his accident. The recent government healthcare insurance market places means that he can now apply for affordable healthcare. This is particularly important as his wife has only a low-paying job. He feels confused by the options available to him and approaches the enrollment process with great trepidation. Like many others, he has left enrollment for the last minute and worries whether he can register in time.

Joe's user stories:

1. As a potential insuree I need to find available insurance policies, to understand what they offer me and how much they will cost.
2. As a novice user I need the MarketPlace system to guide me step-by-step through the application process. **(Usability)**
3. I need the MarketPlace to be online and responsive. **(Availability)**
4. Once I've entered my information and requested a quote I want the quotes to be returned quickly. **(Performance)**
5. I don't want my healthcare record to be made public as this might impact my future employment opportunities. **(Privacy)**
6. I would like to see a side by side comparison of the quotes returned to me.

Per53

Camilla
Campaign Manager

Camilla is a campaign manager with over 15 years of experience in Customer Management. She has excellent and interpersonal and business skills and leads a team of over 100 people.

Topics: Campaign, TargetList, Lead, Contact, Case, Email, Mail

1. As a campaign manager, I need to be able to create a targeted list of customers for a campaign.
2. I need search features to make it easy to add, remove, and purge customers. **(Usability)**
3. I need to be able to manage traditional mailing, email, and phone-based campaigns.
4. As my contact list is large, I need the selection process to be automated.
5. I need import over 50,000 new records and add them to my target list in 10 seconds or less. **(Performance)**
6. As a campaign manager, I need to be able to duplicate a campaign including target list, Duplicate campaigns I would like to be able to duplicate not only the campaign but also the associated target lists.
7. I need to be able to mail merge directly from my target list.
8. As a manager, I need to be able to assign personnel to a campaign.
9. As a SugarCRM user, I need to be able to request new features.

Per54

Sarah
SugarCRM User

Sarah uses SugarCRM in her workplace to manage customers, campaigns, and accounts. She needs effective search mechanisms.

Topics: Search

1. As a SugarCRM user I would like to be able to search for customers using a variety of different fields including but not limited to account name, contact name, phone number, city, state, website.
2. Because some of my search queries are quite complex I would like to be able to save and retrieve the search. This should include both the query and the layout of the results
3. Searches should allow wild cards and regular expressions.
4. Search results should be returned quickly.
5. If my SugarCRM account times-out I would like to be able to log back in and resume my search.
6. Searchable fields and search results should be access controlled – so that they are only available to users with correct access rights.
7. Search features should be integrated into other tasks such as selecting email addresses to add to a list or searching for email messages.

PC25 - Survey-based personas for a target-group-specific consideration of elderly end users of information and communication systems in the German health-care sector

Per55

Monika, born 1952 (65 years old)

In transition to retirement, musicologist

Personal background

- Worked in a church and lectured at a university
- Lives alone in a large rented apartment in a big city
- Her husband died a few years ago and they had no children
- Has contact with her family and the children of her sister

Health situation

- Has no major health issues
- Slighty overweight and sometimes suffers from back pain
- Has a healthy lifestyle with gymnastics and long walks

Health-related information

- Has quite a strong interest in health issues
- No problems searching for information
- Critical toward the public media, since uncertain what is trustworthy
- Trusts especially her family and friends
- Uncertain about information on different treatment methods

Attitude to technical devices

- Has great interest in technical devices, but finds it difficult to handle them
- Feels most secure when using a laptop
- Watches videos online, does online banking, uses e-mail services
- Possesses an e-book reader she barely uses
- Inherited a smartphone and tablet computer from her late husband
- Finds health-related apps horrible because she is afraid of misdiagnosis

PC26 - Modelling agile requirements using context-based persona stories
Per56

Jorge, 38 year old

"I am happy to realize, that my work helps citizens in Andalusia."

Usage behavior – application

usage
low
intensive
○

area
specific function
general function
○

frequency of use
rarely
very often
○

<p>Personal information</p> <p>Job: Project Manager</p> <p>Education: PhD in Software Engineering in Public Administration</p> <p>Nationality: Spanish</p> <p>Languages: Spanish and English</p> <p>Status: Single</p> <p>Hobbies: Philosophy, Literature and travelling with friends</p>	<p>Behavior</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He likes the direct contact with people • He prefers making phone calls rather than writing emails. • He is a methodical person and works in an organized way. <p>Motivation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He is very satisfied when he can optimize the workflows in the Public Administration office 	<p>Requirements for application</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He needs to ensure the usability of the new web application to enable his employees to work with it, without changing their whole work. • He needs workflow based on handling documents in order to map the existing procedures <p>Weak points</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He feels stressed at his job because he has to coordinate the changes among different departments
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PC27 - Engineering software-based motivation: A persona-based approach
Per57 (Ben), Per58 (Clara), Per59 (John), Per60 (Mark), Per61 (Paul), Per62
(Mary)

	Name: Ben	Age: 28	Gender: Male	Job: Programmer
	<p>Overall statement: Ben enjoys competing with the people he knows and are doing similar jobs. It is important for him that the quality of his work is considered in the software-based motivation. He is an explorer and likes to have surprises in his work. He likes to share his achievements with the people he knows and have a friendly competition with them. It is important for him to win big at the end, he thinks that it is not fair for the top winners to receive the same prize as the others.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Conditioning, Tailoring, Suggestion, Tunnelling), Privacy (Detailed Info: Managers, Self – General Info: Peers, Managers, Self – Progress Info: Peers, Managers, Self), Collaboration Nature (Competitive), Performance (Real-time), Feedback (Human generated, Monthly), Incentive (Higher Value, Lower Chance)</p>			
	Name: Clara	Age: 31	Gender: Female	Job: Data Analyst
	<p>Overall statement: The quality of work is important for Clara, however, it is important for her to not fall behind her colleagues. Therefore, she may decrease the quality of her work if she can receive the same points. She is an explorer and wants to have surprises in her work. She is concerned about her detailed work details, however, she finds it helpful for others to be able to access her skills set.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Conditioning, Tailoring, Suggestion), Privacy (Detailed Info: Managers, self – General Info: Everyone – Progress Info: Managers, Self), Collaboration Nature (Collaborative), Performance (Weekly), Feedback (Human generated, Monthly), Incentive (Higher Value, Lower Chance)</p>			
	Name: John	Age: 48	Gender: Male	Job: Accountant
	<p>Overall statement: John is a collaborative person who finds elements introduced by software-based motivation interesting, he likes to share his detailed working information with his relevant colleagues and his skills with everyone within his workplace.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Conditioning, Reduction, Tunnelling, Tailoring), Privacy (Detailed Info:Managers, self – General Info: Everyone), Collaboration Nature (Competitive), Performance (real-time), Feedback (Human generated, weekly), Incentive (Higher Value, Lower Chance)</p>			
	Name: Mark	Age: 42	Gender: Male	Job: Technology Analyst
	<p>Overall statement: Mark cares about the quality of his work and will not decrease the quality if he can get points with lower quality. He is collaborative and doesn't like social recognition. He will keep his points low enough so that he does not attract any attention to himself.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Reduction, Tunnelling, Tailoring, Conditioning), Privacy (Detailed Info: Managers, self- General Info: Everyone, Progress info: self), Collaboration Nature (Competitive), Performance (real-time), Feedback (Human generated, Monthly), Incentive (Lower Value, Higher Chance)</p>			
	Name: Paul	Age: 41	Gender: Male	Job: Recruiter
	<p>Overall statement: Paul does not like software-based motivation, however, if he has to use it, he will get very competitive in order to do his best and be amongst the winners. He just wants to be told what he has to do and doesn't like to make decisions.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Reduction, Tunnelling, Tailoring, Conditioning), Privacy (Detailed Info: Peers, Managers, self – General Info: Everyone), Collaboration Nature (Collaborative), Performance (real-time), Feedback (Computer generated, daily), Incentive (Lower Value, Higher Chance)</p>			
	Name: Mary	Age: 24	Gender: Female	Job: IT Engineer
	<p>Overall statement: Mary is a collaborative, hard-working, privacy sensitive person. She doesn't appreciate elements introduced by software-based motivation and does not find them motivating.</p>			
	<p>Setting: Method (Reduction, Tunnelling, Tailoring), Privacy (Detailed Info:Managers, self – General Info: Peers, Managers, Self), Collaboration Nature (Collaborative), Performance (real-time), Feedback (Human generated, weekly), Incentive (Lower Value, Higher Chance)</p>			

PC28 - Contextualizing user centered design with agile methods in Ethiopia

Per63

Debela (user persona)

Occupation: IT Operator

Gender: Male

Age: 24 years

Education: Debela has Diploma (12 + 3) in accounting. He is a young graduate and has no professional experience.

Language: less skills in using English and Amharic languages but fluent in Afan Oromo which is a working languages of Ethiopia and Oromia region.

Technology: Debela is slow learner. He is eager to know technology but has less experience of using touch phones and has less IT skills. He has learnt basic computer application from a common course in his college. He used to ask his friends for support in operating IT products and for some internet services from the touch phone.

- Debela does not have prior touch phone exposure.

Debela is new to the product (supply chain) and digital payment system. He is to use the application in rural market setting for 4 to 6 hours especially on Tuesday and Saturday (local market days).

Motivation:

The main motivation of using the specific product is in getting salary but also supporting farmers in his area who are illiterate and semi-literate where they have problem of utilizing IT services.

PC29 - Facilitating Idea Generation Using Personas
Per64

	<p>Persona:</p> <p>Miss Tsun-tsun Ji</p> <p>42 years old, Taichung city Office lady 8 hours a day on the computer. Nature, organic life, cooking</p>
	<p>Product /service concept:</p> <p>Beauty Alarm Service</p> <p>Features: alarm service for regular beauty care.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A web-based service 2. Send short message to members 3. Customized service by member.
	<p>Scenario:</p> <p>It is time to drink water</p> <p>Miss Ji is an office lady. Busy with her daily job, she tries to balance between mind and body, as her means to stay beautiful. She wishes somebody can remind her to do beauty care.</p> <p>It is 1pm, she gets a message from BEAUTY ALARM service on her mobile phone, "It is time to have some water. More water, prettier!"</p>

PC30 - Improving the Withdrawal Functionality on ATM Using a UCD Framework. A Case Study

Per65

Roberto Campos

My business is my priority, my goal is to satisfy my clients and work well with my partners.

Demographics

Age: 40
Gender: Male
Marital Status: Married
Income: 6000 soles
Location: Lima

Defining Traits

- Persistence
- Take risks
- Trustful

Professional Background

Education
Businessman

Company / Job Title
Clothing Perú / Manager (Own business)

Work Experience
More than 10 years working on his own business, and small clothing store placed in the biggest clothing shopping center of Peru, Gamarra.

Personal Preferences

Interests
He likes football on the weekends, perform open-air activities with his two daughters. Invest his money in high quality clothing. He wishes to study a Master.

Needs
Needs cash to make transactions with another businessmen in the agitated Gamarra. The frequently withdrawn amount is 1000 soles. He uses the ATM near to his store.

Psychographics

Values
Quality releases
Disciplined
Honest

Goals
Make his store bigger
Study a master in Business Management

Challenges & Frustrations
Interaction with no financial people.
Keep the finances of his business in well state.

Communication Style

Casual Professional
General Technical

Carla Sanchez

Between work and college, I always need cash to pay a thousand things

Professional Background

Education
Architecture student in Pedro Ruiz Gallo University

Company / Job Title
"Unico Arquitectos" / Intern

Work Experience
In an internship in "Unico Arquitectos".

Psychographics

Values
Balance between job and college.
Compromise
Responsibility

Goals
Finish college in the stablished times.

Challenges & Frustrations
Spend a lot in architecture materials.
Stay on a budget.

Demographics

Age: 20

Gender: Female

Marital Status: Single

Income: 1200 soles

Location: Chiclayo

Personal Preferences

Interests
She likes the cinema and videogames in her free time.
Exercises three times a week. Often makes small trips.

Needs
Need always cash in hands to buy the architecture materials for college. Also, to pay for food. Need bills of lower denomination to easily have spare change.

Defining Traits

1. Enthusiastic
2. Creative
3. Disciplined

Communication Style

Casual Professional

General Technical

PC31 - Requirements specification of a software-intensive system in the health domain: An experience report

Per67

Mateus (Anesthetist)	
	<p>Motto: Patient safety</p> <p>Description: Mateus, 50 years, married, is an anesthetist doctor with 15 years of experience. He works in ICESP's surgical center since his residency. Although he is able to do his functions well, he believes that some changes would make his work easier and would improve patient safety.</p>
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To have OR equipment internally integrated, to visualize all patient data in a unique monitor with friendly interface [BV5] [BV6] [BV7] [BV13]• To have high data integration between OR, pre-anesthetic and post-anesthetic data [BV1][BV19]• To reduce the manual register on anesthesia records [BV2]• To have an automated register of data generated by OR equipment [BV3]• To improve the communication with professionals of technologies areas, to have a better maintenance of OR equipment [BV4] [BV6] [BV9]• To store integrated data of the patient and the surgery in repositories or databases [BV1] [BV2]• To use equipments inside OR that have automated feedback mechanisms [BV8]• To use equipments inside the OR that need less cables [BV7]	

Per68

Paulo (General coordinator)	
	<p>Motto: To optimize resources of the HC's anesthesia division</p> <p>Description: Paulo, 65 years, married, is an anesthetist doctor with 30 years of experience. Nowadays, he is the general coordinator of the Hospital das Clinicas complex's anesthesia division. He is responsible for resources distribution between the complex's institutes.</p>
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To have an integrated system between the HC complex's institutes to allow the access to every patient records [BV1] [BV19]• To have an system with data about the human resources and equipment to ease the HC complex management as a whole [BV1] [BV5] [BV11] [BV18]	

Per69

Sofia (Surgical Center Coordinator)	
	<p>Motto: To optimize resources in the surgical center</p> <p>Description: Sofia, 45 years, married, is an anesthetist doctor with 19 years of experience. Nowadays, she is coordinator of the ICESP's Surgical Center. She performs activities such as rooms allocation and resources distribution at ICESP.</p>
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• To have an integrated system to data transit between surgical center sectors [BV1] [BV19]• To have a digital system that stores all the generated data, excluding the use of physical records [BV1] [BV2]• To have an electronic record system with a friendly interface and with more ease to insert data [BV1] [BV6] [BV9]• To facilitate the hospital beds and ORs management [BV10] [BV12] [BV14]• To have an human resource system with needed data to plan professionals' training [BV11] [BV17]	

PC32 - Building an Educational Product: Constructive Alignment and Requirements Engineering

Per70

Jamal is male and 25 years old. He comes from a historically Muslim culture, with traditionally strong family ties. Currently, he is staying away from the family and relatives due to having studies and job. He is an active user of educational mobile apps, such as Duolingo, watches YouTube habitually. Jamal wants to keep in touch with his family and friends, and feels that it's important. However, he has various reasons preventing him from doing so such as being busy, forgetful, and having other priorities such as work and studies.

PC33 - Stop Anxiety: Tackling Anxiety in the Academic Campus Through an mHealth Multidisciplinary User-Centred Approach

Per71

Image adapted from pxhere.

Rute is 20 years old and is currently completing the second year of her degree in Nursing, at the University of Aveiro. She spends much of her time studying for her exams, which is something that always made her very anxious. Although Rute spends a large part of her day trying to study, she often faces blockages that prevent her from progressing, eventually becoming even more anxious than she already is. Despite the adaptation struggles that Rute was faced with, in her first year of college, she still considers that the evaluation periods are the hardest. During her studies, and moments before the start of her exams, Rute normally begins to sweat from her hands, to tremble, and she feels an heavy chest. Sometimes, during the course of her exams, these symptoms are accompanied by blanks, which consequently prevent her from applying the knowledge she knows she has.

Motivation: Rute would like to get the grades that she so hardly worked for by learning how to deal with her anxiety attacks during the course of her exams.

Per72

Image adapted from pxhere.

Carlos is a 47 year old college teacher who has taught at the University of Aveiro for 10 years. During his free time he enjoys doing activities, such as spending time with his children, traveling, going to the gym, reading the newspaper, and socializing with his family and friends. Typically, at the end of each day, due to the stress that comes from his work, he arrives home very tired. Carlos feels that he is overwhelmed by an immense amount of work, which occupies most of his time, and he feels his work is not valued enough.

Motivation: Carlos would like to learn about some techniques and procedures that could help him deal with his daily anxiety and stress, particularly in a way that could be available during his daily routines.

PC34 - The Requirement Analysis for Developing the Assisted Living Technology for the Elderly

Per73

Grandma Lin

Age: 72 years old

Gender: female

Occupation: retired teacher

Habits: go hiking

Residence: Taipei, Taiwan

Marriage: her husband passed away recently, lives with son currently

Education: B.S.

Mood changes: She previously liked to help others, optimistic and usually hanged out with husband to enjoy nice food and tourist spot. However, she becomes lonely and sad after her husband passed away.

- **Life:**

After retiring from high school, she lived happily with his family. She usually went to many tourist spots and went hiking with her husband to enjoy their wonderful life. However, after her husband passed away two years ago due to heart attack, she became sad and lonely. Her body condition changed a lot during these two years.

- **Body condition:**

She has been diagnosed with diabetes and hypertension, which were controlled by medication. She also got mild memory problems. Her son mentioned that she could not find out some important things at home recently. She sometimes forgets to have drugs and even forgets to eat meals. The meal preparation is also difficult for her.

Susan Wang

Age: 37 years old

Gender: female

Occupation: housekeeper

Habits: shopping

Residence: Tainan, Taiwan

Marriage: married

Education: B.S.

Family: live with husband, 4-year-old-child, and husband's parents

Mood changes:

- Her life changed a lot after getting married.
- She becomes emotional since too much loads of taking care for the family.

- **Life:** She needs to take care for the 4-year-old daughter and the parents of her husband, therefore, she can not have time for herself.
- **Difficulties as a caregiver:** Because her father-in-law and mother-in-law have different diseases, she needs to prepares different meals and medications for them. Sometimes she gets confused of the different needs of them. In addition, because she has to take care for the child simultaneously, she feels too busy to finish all tasks by herself.

PC35 - User Requirements for Inclusive Technology for Older Adults

Per75 - Per88

No.	Description of persona
1	<i>Tom</i> is a 68-year-old man who lives with his wife. Tom lives in Byker, Newcastle. Tom has quite an active social life and enjoys meeting new people.
2	<i>George</i> is an 81-year-old man who lives alone. He lives in Newcastle. George is quite active and enjoys helping others.
3	<i>Anthony</i> is a 75-year-old man who lives alone. He lives in sheltered housing near Gateshead town center. He lives a quiet life and doesn't get out much. Two or three times a week he walks to the local superstore to buy groceries.
4	<i>Isabella</i> is an 89-year-old woman who lives alone. She lives in Newcastle City Center. She is not as active as she used to be because her eyesight is getting worse and she worries about losing her way.
5	<i>Sarah</i> is a 72-year-old woman who lives with her husband. She lives in a small house in Corbridge. Sarah enjoys living in the rural community and has a small number of friends who live nearby.
6	<i>Michael</i> is a 72-year-old man who lives alone. Michael lives in Felling, Gateshead. For the past few years, he has found mobility very difficult and he is waiting for a hip operation. Consequently, he doesn't get out much.
7	<i>Isabel</i> is an 82-year-old woman who has lived alone for the past two years. She lives in a flat by herself in Newcastle. She no longer goes out very often and has become very physically inactive. Her daughter brings her groceries once a week.
8	<i>Fatima</i> is a 73-year-old lady who lives with her husband. She lives in Hexham. She is reasonably active and enjoys using her walker to help her get around.
9	<i>Dorothy</i> is a 69-year-old woman who lives alone. She lives in Blaydon. Dorothy uses a walker to get around because she finds that it gives her confidence after her fall one year ago.
10	<i>Manuel</i> is a 74-year-old man who lives alone. He lives in an apartment in Madrid. He recently suffered a bad fall which has made it difficult for him to get around. He is undergoing therapy at a local falls clinic and is slowly getting better.
11	<i>Manuela</i> is an 83-year-old woman who lives with her husband in a nursing home in Getafe, Madrid. She has lost some sight during the last years, and she does not know her way around the new neighborhood or the venues and activities there.
12	<i>Jose</i> is an 80-year-old man who lives alone. He lives in a small, old flat in Getafe, Madrid. José was quite active before the fracture, and enjoyed going in the morning to a bar near his house with his friends.
13	<i>David</i> is a 75-year-old man who has recovered from a fracture and currently he is able to walk assisted by a normal walker.
14	<i>Ana</i> is a 76-year-old woman who has some blood pressure problems. She lives in a nursing home and needs a crutch to walk after a fall.

Patient 1: Bob (imaginary person) is a 20-year-old male. He sustained a high-level cervical SCI during a skiing accident. It has been three months since his injury. He was initially on a mechanical ventilator, and now he can tolerate the speaking cuff. He could only communicate through lip signals for the first two months while he was on a ventilator. Now he can speak; however, he struggles with long conversations due to ventilatory muscle fatigue and frequent dry throat. It is also challenging for him to speak in noisy environments since he struggles with maintaining voice intensity. In addition, due to the cervical SCI, he has minimal hand movement and sensation.

Patient 2: Trudy (imaginary person) is a 45-year-old female with an SCI. It has been five years since her injury. She has minimal upper-body movements. As a result, she cannot move her fingers to write or type. However, she has no major problem with her speech. Though she tends to fatigue earlier than non-disabled participants during long conversations, she can continue the conversation with pauses.

PC37 - User-Centered Development of a Public Transportation Vehicle Operated in a Demand-Responsive Environment

Per91

Ingrid Henke, 73 years old, pensioner

"I only drive the car if I have to"

Residence

Household size

Traffic behaviour

spontaneous planned

Means of transport

Means of communication

About Ingrid

Ingrid is a retired nurse and has lived with her husband in her house for over 30 years. Routines are important to her, e.g. every Tuesday and Saturday she takes the bus to the market. Ingrid is reluctant to go by car because she has problems with her eyes. When shopping or going on excursions with her grandchildren, her husband usually drives.

Hobbies/Interests

She is glad about:

- pedestrian zones with green areas
- wide, clear sidewalks
- short routes
- large score and information boards

She is angry about:

- distant stops and long footpaths
- Loud passengers in the bus

She wants:

- reliability in PT
- stops in the immediate vicinity
- comfortable transport

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PC38 - Lessons Learned from Applying Requirements and Design Techniques in the Development of a Machine Learning System for Predicting Lawsuits Against Power Companies

Per92

Persona 1: Jane is 40 years old and has 3 children. A power blackout caused her refrigerator to break, and also two fans, which she and her family use during hot days. She reported the problem to the power company, aiming at receiving the corresponding refund. However, she received no response. As a result, she files for a lawsuit against the power company due to lack of or late attendance. Our chatbot could ask Jane if, after a blackout, there is a need to request repairs or request refunds. Also, if a request is being processed, the chatbot can inform Jane how long it will take for her to receive an answer and what are the stages of her request within the company.

Per93

Persona 2: Anne is 25 years old and is studying online to get a masters degree. Power blackouts are becoming more common due to the rainy season in the city. A proper analysis of the electric structure could avoid blackout problems, so Anne decides to request an electric infrastructure check-up. The fact that there is no feedback on the repair request makes her very angry, which causes her to file a lawsuit against the power company. The chatbot could analyze that Anne has frequent blackouts and ask, before she does, if she wants to request an electric infrastructure check-up. Also, if a request is being processed, the chatbot can inform Anne how long it will take for her to receive a reply or the date in which a technician will go to her house.

PC39 - Design, Code, Stitch, Wear, and Show It! Mobile Visual Pattern Design in School Contexts
Per94

Amelie, 14 years

LOCATION
Graz, Austria

SIBLINGS
1 brother

SCHOOL
8-th grade

FAVORITE SUBJECT
Sports, English

GOOD AT
drawing

NOT GOOD AT
math, singing

DESIRED CAREER
interior architect

INTERESTS
dancing, swimming, browsing on her smartphone

SMARTPHONE OWNERSHIP
4 years, uses it every day

PROGRAMMING SKILLS
Scratch, robot programming workshop

FAVORITE APPS

“I am creative and trendy. I like to go shopping and pay a lot attention to my appearance.”

Amelie has painted a t-shirt before, but never designed one online. She loves designs like flowers, animals, and slogans on her clothes.

Per95

Julian, 13 years

LOCATION
Hart bei Graz, Austria

SIBLINGS
1 sister

SCHOOL
7-th grade

FAVORITE SUBJECT
Sports, Computer Science

GOOD AT
sports

NOT GOOD AT
school

DESIRED CAREER
technical profession

INTERESTS
Sports in general, Music, Wakeboarding, Computers

SMARTPHONE OWNERSHIP
Android phone for 5 years

PROGRAMMING SKILLS
Scratch at school and freetime

FAVORITE APPS

“I don't really care about fashion. I choose the clothes I wear by myself, but I don't like to go shopping, my mother and my sister do that for me.”

Julian has painted a t-shirt before, but never designed one online. He likes brands such as Nike or Adidas on his jacket.

PC40 - Virtual Reality Enabled Human-Centric Requirements Engineering
Per96

PC41 - Towards User Generated AR Experiences: Enable consumers to generate their own AR experiences for planning indoor spaces

Per97

Annika Ström
Female, 44
Stockholm, Sweden
Married, two children
Interior designer/Saleswoman for a home furnishing store chain

“Can you send me some photos of the room and an idea of what colours you like? I can put a few initial ideas together and we can discuss from there.”

Relevant characteristics

- Service-minded, good social skills
- Good at thinking from the perspective of others
- Keeps up-to-date on the latest trends
- Extensive experience of furniture products (has worked many years as a salesperson).

Usage context

- On location (at a customer’s house/flat/office), typically with a mobile or tablet – to gather data, present suggestions.
- At the office (back office to a furniture store) – to plan/design.
- When meeting customers in-store – to demo ideas.

Scenarios

- Annika is visiting a customer’s house. The customer is renovating all the downstairs rooms in their house (kitchen, dining room, living room, hallway) and wants ideas for wallpaper/paint colour and a complete set of living room and dining room furniture. They want to keep their existing coffee table, TV and piano (all are in the living room today).
- Annika is visiting a customer’s flat. The customer has two children who are currently sharing one large bedroom. They plan to split the bedroom into two smaller bedrooms and have given her a rough plan drawing. In each room they’ll need new wallpaper, new bed, new desk and wardrobe, plus other furnishings/decoration as appropriate. Annika needs to scan in measurements for the room and then visualize some alternatives for how the two rooms would look.
- A customer has come into the store and wants help in choosing new furniture for their living room. They have already used the ‘Atlantis’ app to scan in their existing living room and furniture...

Key needs

- Possibility to scan a whole property and have floorplans generated based on that.
- Possibility to empty rooms of all existing furnishings/decorations except those that the customer wishes to keep.
- Possibility to add a partial/full room separator, wall section, or even split a room.
- Possibility to collaborate on plans with customers.
- Show wallpaper designs and store furniture in a customer’s room (VR/AR).
- Complete ‘shopping list’ for all room plans in a home.

Sarah Jones

Female, 49
Berlin, Germany
Single

Lives in a 1-bedroom apartment (rental)

"I like to update and re-plan my living room depending on the season"

Relevant characteristics

- Very active
- Attention to detail
- Fussy about colours
- Likes change

Usage context

- In living room - has limited space (not much free floor space unless furniture is moved).
- iPad only (does not have a laptop/desktop).

Scenarios

- Spring is in the air and it is starting to get lighter outside. Sara wants to re-organise her living room so that the TV doesn't get direct sunlight and that she can look directly outside from her sofa.
- Sarah wants to put some family pictures on the wall but isn't sure where to place them / how they will look. She also wants to ensure they are at roughly the right height for people to view comfortably when standing in front of them.
- One of the legs of her coffee table is loose and Sara has decided to buy a new one. She would like one that is a similar style/size/material but with rounded corners instead of sharp ones, and more sturdy legs!
- In conjunction with the new coffee table Sara is thinking about buying an additional floor lamp and wants to explore lamps that might suit. Ideally she'd like to see how well they would light up the room with different strengths of lightbulbs.
- Sarah has a small spare room that today she uses mainly for storage. She wants to have a temporary bed solution for visitors and is wondering what it would look like to have a small sofa-bed or foldout cupboard-bed in the room.
- Sarah is considering moving an old armchair from her living room into the spare room – she is wondering what it would look like and whether there will be enough space.

Key needs

- Visualize many different alternative layouts to her living room without having to move furniture around.
- Re-use of a significant amount of existing furniture in her plans (possibly no or just the odd item of new furniture).
- To visualize how changes would look without any impact on the apartment itself until plans are final (e.g. to see how a set of pictures would look on her wall without having to create any holes in the wall until she knows she has the right arrangement).